

Comparison of Safety and Efficacy of Metformin and Vildagliptin versus Metformin and Glimpiride in Patients of Type - 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM)

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Abstract

Introduction: The common medication used to treat diabetes is metformin. Add-on therapy is advised if metformin is unable to effectively manage blood glucose levels. Dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors and an incretin-based therapy have emerged as significant supplementary medications in Type - 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), replacing the usual and gold standard of adding a sulfonylurea to metformin to achieve tight glycaemic control. In order to assess and evaluate the efficacy and safety of vildagliptin-metformin versus glimepiride-metformin in patients with T2DM who were not satisfactorily managed with metformin alone, the current study was designed.

Materials and Methods: A total of 30 patients were assigned to each of the glimepiride-metformin and vildagliptin-metformin groups. The study lasted for three months. At 0 week, 6 weeks, and 12 weeks, fasting plasma glucose, postprandial plasma glucose, adverse events were reported. Glycosylated haemoglobin levels were measured at 0 and 12 weeks.

Result: When vildagliptin-metformin was compared to glimepiride-metformin, there was a substantial reduction in mean FBS, PPBS levels, and HbA1c% from baseline. The glimepiride metformin group was associated with considerably higher hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal problems, and weight gain than the vildagliptin-metformin group.

Conclusion: The vildagliptin-metformin combination produced equivalent glucose control to the glimepiride-metformin combination. It also resulted in a lower risk of hypoglycemia, gastrointestinal symptoms, and weight gain, as well as an improved adverse event profile.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes, Metformin, Vildagliptin, Glimpiride, FBG, PPBG, HbA1C, ADR's.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a prevalent chronic non communicable disease characterised by elevated blood glucose levels. [1] Diabetes mellitus is a major public health issue that affects over 400 million individuals worldwide. Diabetic patients are increasing on a yearly basis, with a total of 629 million projected by 2045. [2]

Diabetes is divided into two types: type 1 and type 2, often known as insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM) and non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM). Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is caused by insufficient insulin synthesis by pancreatic beta cells. [3]

The significant burden of type 2 diabetes mellitus is closely related to diabetes-related macrovascular complications such as ischemic heart disease, stroke, and peripheral vascular disease, as well as amputations, as well as microvascular changes that lead to blindness, renal failure, and peripheral neuropathy. [4-6]

If a single anti-diabetic medicine failed to manage blood plasma levels, many individuals need more than one oral medication to achieve the best outcomes. Combination medications produce significantly superior benefits in newly diabetic people. Many novel anti-diabetic medications have recently been discovered. [7-9]

In non-obese diabetics, sulfonylureas are usually the first-line treatment option, while metformin is used in obese diabetics. Because of its inexpensive cost, the combination of metformin and sulfonylureas is most often used in India and can achieve a higher reduction in haemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) than either medicine alone. [10] This combo therapy, however, is associated with weight gain and severe hypoglycemia. Despite well-planned dose regimens using oral hypoglycemic agents (OHAs), some

Type 2 diabetic patients have poor glycemic control, and many OHAs cause adverse drug reactions (ADRs) such as weight gain and hypoglycemia. In this context, the search for better OHAs is ongoing.

The role of "incretins," notably glucagon-like peptide (GLP-I), has recently been established. In response to an increase in plasma glucose, the peptide GLP-I enhances insulin secretion while decreasing glucagon levels. However, due to its very short plasma t_{1/2} (2 minutes) and chemical composition, this peptide hormone cannot be taken orally. To extend the duration of action of endogenous GLP-I, drugs that inhibit dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP 4), the enzyme responsible for GLP -1 metabolic breakdown, have been developed. Vildagliptin is a strong, specific, and reversible DPP-4 inhibitor that improves glycemic control in Type 2 diabetes patients (T2DM). [11-12]

The aim of the present study is to find the safety and efficacy of vildagliptin (50 mg) with metformin (500 mg) with comparison of glimepiride (2 mg) with metformin (500 mg) for type-2 diabetes mellitus patients.

Materials and Methods

The current study was a randomised, open-label, comparative study undertaken by the department of pharmacology in the General Medicine OPD at Viswabharathi General Hospital in Kurnool between January 2021 and December 2022. The study was approved by the institution's ethical committee.

Patients with poor glycemic control who were currently taking metformin 500 mg daily were eligible for this research. The study included males and females aged 40 to 70 years with Type 2 diabetes already on therapy but with uncontrolled blood sugars, i.e., (fasting blood sugar [FBS] >126 mg/dl and postprandial blood sugar (PPBS) >200 mg/dl)

Pregnant women, breastfeeding women, neonates, infants, and elderly (>70 years) patients, as well as those suffering from type 1 diabetes mellitus, chronic renal or hepatic problems, and getting insulin treatment, were excluded from the study.

All participants provided written informed consent were enrolled into study. Total of 60 patients were divided into two groups of 30, each with 30 patients. Patients in the GM (glimepiride- metformin) group were given glimepiride 1 mg bid and metformin 500 mg bid.

Patients in the VM (vildagliptin- metformin) group were given vildagliptin 50 mg bid and metformin 500 mg bid. At the end of each month, blood sugar levels (both fasting and postprandial) were tested on a regular basis. Blood glucose and HbA1c levels were measured at the baseline and at the end of the study. Adverse events like hypoglycemia,

weight gain, and general gastrointestinal symptoms such as nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea, flatulence, and abdominal discomfort were recorded.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 22. Mean \pm standard deviations & frequencies were calculated for quantitative variables. The means and frequencies of variables were evaluated using unpaired Student's *t*-test and the chi-square test, respectively. $P < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant.

Result

A total of 60 patients were enrolled in the study with an age range between 40 to 70 years. It was found that age, sex and BMI did not vary significantly among the 2 groups. (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of two treatment groups

Variable	Group GM	Group VM	p-value
Age (Years)	51.32 \pm 8.12	51.86 \pm 8.92	0.71
Sex			
Male	16	17	0.09
Female	14	13	
BMI	26.2 \pm 7.8	24.6 \pm 6.9	0.54

Baseline parameters like FBG, PPBG and HbA1c did not vary significantly among the 2 groups. (Table 2)

Table 2: Baseline laboratory parameters in two treatment groups.

Variable	Group GM	Group VM	p-value
FBG (mg/dl)	173.52 \pm 21.23	161.8 \pm 19.78	0.34
PPBG (mg/dl)	272.42 \pm 51.72	261.35 \pm 53.87	0.08
HbA1c (%)	8.3 \pm 1.1	7.9 \pm 1.0	0.71

The mean values of FBG in the two groups at baseline, 6 weeks and 12 weeks of treatment is shown in Table 3. The mean reduction in in FBG in VM group was higher than in the GM group which was statistically significant.

Table 3: Fasting blood glucose (mg/dl) in two treatment groups.

Variable	Group GM	Group VM	p-value
Baseline	173.52 \pm 21.23	161.8 \pm 19.78	0.001*
6 weeks	130.92 \pm 15.14	125.45 \pm 14.21	0.03*
12 weeks	118.54 \pm 13.48	112.83 \pm 6.18	0.002*

The mean values of PPBG in the two groups at baseline, 6 weeks and 12 weeks of treatment is shown in Table 4. The mean reduction in in PPBG in VM group was higher than in the GM group which was statistically significant.

Table 4: Postprandial blood glucose (mg/dl) in two treatment groups.

Variable	Group GM	Group VM	p-value
Baseline	272.42±51.72	261.35±53.87	0.001*
6 weeks	223.80±45.76	221.14±47.87	0.001*
12 weeks	188.93±35.62	179.12±37.65	0.002*

The mean reduction in inHbA1c in VM group was higher than in the GM group which was statistically significant (Table 5)

Table 5: HbA1c in two treatment groups

Variable	Group GM	Group VM	p-value
Baseline	8.15±0.65	8.04±0.45	0.02*
12 weeks	7.14±0.72	7.09±0.82	0.01*

The comparative data regarding the number of patients who reported adverse events in the two groups is shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Adverse drug reactions in two treatment groups

Adverse drug reactions	Group GM (N=30)	Group VM (N=30)	P value
Hypoglycemia	11	1	0.01*
Gastrointestinal symptoms	10	3	0.02*
Weight gain	5	0	0.01*

Discussion

Metformin is recommended as first-line therapy for T2DM by American Diabetes Association (ADA) and International Diabetic Federation (IDF) guidelines. [13,14] However, because T2DM is a progressive disease, combination treatments with complementary mechanisms of action are frequently required to meet glycemic objectives and avoid long-term consequences. [15]

For decades, combining metformin with a sulfonylurea has been the gold standard. [16] However, its use is usually linked to weight gain and severe hypoglycemia episodes. [17] Modest and sustained weight loss has been found to enhance glycemic control in T2DM individuals who are overweight or obese. In multiple investigations, hypoglycemic incidents in T2DM patients have been linked

to cognitive impairment, dementia, morbidity, and mortality. [14] When selecting antidiabetic drugs, current treatment guidelines propose a patient-centered strategy that takes into account criteria such as effectiveness, tolerability, long-term safety, cost, and patient preferences. As a result, in patients with T2DM who are uncontrolled with metformin monotherapy, it is critical to investigate the inclusion of a second antidiabetic medication that improves glycemic control without raising the risk of hypoglycemia episodes or weight gain. [18] Vildagliptin, a powerful selective DPP-4 inhibitor, improves glycemic management by increasing the availability of endogenous incretin hormones such as GLP-1 and GIP. It increases glucose-dependent insulin secretion while suppressing glucagon

release, complementing the pharmacological impact of metformin by lowering the risk of weight gain and hypoglycemia. [19].

In the current study, individuals taking vildagliptin and metformin together experienced a substantial decrease in mean FBS and PPBS. The findings are analogous to those of Bosi *et al.*, [20], who found a significant decrease in FBS and PPBS levels, and Pan *et al.*, [21], who found a significant reduction in fasting blood glucose (FBG) levels ($P < 0.05$) when metformin and vildagliptin were combined.

The patients on vildagliptin and metformin in the current study had a substantial decrease in mean HbA1c from baseline to the end of the study. Our findings are consistent with those of Bosi *et al.*, Pan *et al.*, and Ved and Shah. [20,21 & 22]

The combination of vildagliptin and metformin resulted in decreased weight gain and mild hypoglycemia, demonstrating the safety of combination medication use. Similar findings were reported in our prior research of an add-on combination of vildagliptin and metformin, which showed promising efficacy. [23].

We found that glimepiride + metformin produced higher hypoglycemia than vildagliptin + metformin, which is consistent with Matthews DR *et al.* [24] and Ahrén B *et al.* [25]. Gastrointestinal symptoms were considerably worse in the vildagliptin + metformin group compared to the glimepiride + metformin group; comparable findings were obtained in the HJ *et al.* trial. [26]. Weight increase is found in persons taking glimepiride plus metformin. The findings were consistent with those reported in earlier studies involving vildagliptin and metformin. [27]

Conclusion

This study shows that vildagliptin added to metformin could be a better compared to

glimepiride added to metformin in the treatment of type II diabetes due to improved blood glucose control, fewer side effects, and a lower risk of hypoglycaemia, weight gain.

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